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CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK BASED FEATURE EXTRACTION FOR IRIS RECOGNITION

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ABSTRACT

Iris is a powerful tool for reliable human identification. It has the potential to identify individuals with a high degree of assurance. Extracting good features is the most significant step in the iris recognition system. In the past, different features have been used to implement iris recognition system. Most of them are depend on hand-crafted features designed by biometrics specialists. Due to the success of deep learning in computer vision problems, the features learned by the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) have gained much attention to be applied for iris recognition system. In this paper, we evaluate the extracted learned features from a pre-trained Convolutional Neural Network (Alex-Net Model) followed by a multi-class Support Vector Machine (SVM) algorithm to perform classification. The performance of the proposed system is investigated when extracting features from the segmented iris image and from the normalized iris image. The proposed iris recognition system is tested on four public datasets IITD, iris databases CASIAIris-V1, CASIA-Iris-thousand and, CASIA-Iris- V3 Interval. The system achieved excellent results with the very high accuracy rate.

KEYWORDS

Biometrics, Iris, Recognition, Deep learning, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Feature extraction (FE).

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FUTURE AND CHALLENGES OF INTERNET OF THINGS

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ABSTRACT

The world is moving forward at a fast pace, and the credit goes to ever growing technology. One such concept is IOT (Internet of things) with which automation is no longer a virtual reality. IOT connects various non-living objects through the internet and enables them to share information with their community network to automate processes for humans and makes their lives easier. The paper presents the future challenges of IoT, such as the technical (connectivity, compatibility and longevity, standards, intelligent analysis and actions, security), business (investment, modest revenue model etc.), societal (changing demands, new devices, expense, customer confidence etc.) and legal challenges (laws, regulations, procedures, policies etc.). A section also discusses the various myths that might hamper the progress of IOT, security of data being the most critical factor of all. An optimistic approach to people in adopting the unfolding changes brought by IOT will also help in its growth.

KEYWORDS

IoT, Internet of Things, Security, Sensors

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DATA MINING MODEL PERFORMANCE OF SALES PREDICTIVE ALGORITHMS BASED ON RAPIDMINER WORKFLOWS

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ABSTRACT

By applying RapidMiner workflows has been processed a dataset originated from different data files, and containing information about the sales over three years of a large chain of retail stores. Subsequently, has been constructed a Deep Learning model performing a predictive algorithm suitable for sales forecasting. This model is based on artificial neural network –ANN- algorithm able to learn the model starting from sales historical data and by pre-processing the data. The best built model uses a multilayer neural network together with an “optimized operator” able to find automatically the best parameter setting of the implemented algorithm. In order to prove the best performing predictive model, other machine learning algorithms have been tested. The performance comparison has been performed between Support Vector Machine –SVM-, k-Nearest Neighbor k-NN-, Gradient Boosted Trees, Decision Trees, and Deep Learning algorithms. The comparison of the degree of correlation between real and predicted values, the average absolute error and the relative average error proved that ANN exhibited the best performance. The Gradient Boosted Trees approach represents an alternative approach having the second best performance. The case of study has been developed within the framework of an industry project oriented on the integration of high performance data mining models able to predict sales using–ERP- and customer relationship management –CRM- tools.

KEYWORDS

RapidMiner, Neural Network, Deep Learning, Gradient Boosted Trees, Data Mining Performance, Sales Prediction.

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CLUSTERING ALGORITHM FOR A HEALTHCARE DATASET USING SILHOUETTE SCORE VALUE

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ABSTRACT

The huge amount of healthcare data, coupled with the need for data analysis tools has made data mining interesting research areas. Data mining tools and techniques help to discover and understand hidden patterns in a dataset which may not be possible by mainly visualization of the data. Selecting appropriate clustering method and optimal number of clusters in healthcare data can be confusing and difficult most times. Recently, a large number of clustering algorithms are available for clustering healthcare data, but it is very difficult for people with little knowledge of data mining to choose suitable clustering algorithms. This paper aims to analyze clustering techniques using healthcare dataset, in order to determine suitable algorithms which can bring the optimized group clusters. Performances of two clustering algorithms (Kmeans and DBSCAN) were compared using Silhouette score values. Firstly, we analyzed K-means algorithm using different number of clusters (K) and different distance metrics. Secondly, we analyzed DBSCAN algorithm using different minimum number of points required to form a cluster (minPts) and different distance metrics. The experimental result indicates that both K-means and DBSCAN algorithms have strong intra-cluster cohesion and inter-cluster separation. Based on the analysis, K-means algorithm performed better compare to DBSCAN algorithm in terms of clustering accuracy and execution time.

KEYWORDS

Dataset, Clustering, Healthcare data, Silhouette score value, K-means, DBSCAN

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DETECTION OF MALARIA PARASITE IN GIEMSA BLOOD SAMPLE USING IMAGE PROCESSING

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ABSTRACT

Malaria is one of the deadliest diseases ever exists in this planet. Automated evaluation process can notably decrease the time needed for diagnosis of the disease. This will result in early onset of treatment saving many lives. As it poses a serious global health problem, we approached to develop a model to detect malaria parasite accurately from giemsa blood sample with the hope of reducing death rate because of malaria. In this work, we developed a model by using color based pixel discrimination technique and Segmentation operation to identify malaria parasites from thin smear blood images. Various egmentation techniques like watershed segmentation, HSV segmentation have been used in this method to decrease the false result in the area of malaria detection. We believe that, our malaria parasite detection method will be helpful wherever it is difficult to find the expert in microscopic analysis of blood report and also limits the human error while detecting the presence of parasites in the blood sample.

KEYWORDS

Malaria, HSV segmentation, Watershed segmentation, Giemsa blood sample, RBC.

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AN ALGORITHM FOR PREDICTIVE DATA MINING APPROACH IN MEDICAL DIAGNOSIS

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ABSTRACT

The Healthcare industry contains big and complex data that may be required in order to discover fascinating pattern of diseases & makes effective decisions with the help of different machine learning techniques. Advanced data mining techniques are used to discover knowledge in database and for medical research. This paper has analyzed prediction systems for Diabetes, Kidney and Liver disease using more number of input attributes. The data mining classification techniques, namely Support Vector Machine(SVM) and Random Forest (RF) are analyzed on Diabetes, Kidney and Liver disease database. The performance of these techniques is compared, based on precision, recall, accuracy, f_measure as well as time. As a result of study the proposed algorithm is designed using SVM and RF algorithm and the experimental result shows the accuracy of 99.35%, 99.37 and 99.14 on diabetes, kidney and liver disease respectively.

KEYWORDS

Data Mining, Clinical Decision Support System, Disease Prediction, Classification, SVM, RF.

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MULTI-CORE PROCESSORS: CONCEPTS AND IMPLEMENTATIONS

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ABSTRACT

This research paper aims at comparing two multi-core processors machines, the Intel core i7-4960X processor (Ivy Bridge E) and the AMD Phenom II X6. It starts by introducing a single-core processor machine to motivate the need for multi-core processors. Then, it explains the multi-core processor machine and the issues that rises in implementing them. It also provides a real life example machines such as TILEPro64 and Epiphany-IV 64-core 28nm Microprocessor (E64G401). The methodology that was used in comparing the Intel core i7 and AMD phenom II processors starts by explaining how processors' performance are measured, then by listing the most important and relevant technical specification to the comparison. After that, running the comparison by using different metrics such as power, the use of HyperThreading technology, the operating frequency, the use of AES encryption and decryption, and the different characteristics of cache memory such as the size, classification, and its memory controller. Finally, reaching to a roughly decision about which one of them has a better over all performance.

KEYWORDS

Single-core processor, multi-core processors, Intel core i7, AMD phenom, Hyper-Threading.

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A COMPARISON OF CACHE REPLACEMENT ALGORITHMS FOR VIDEO SERVICES

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ABSTRACT

The increasing demand for video services has made video caching a necessity to decrease download times and reduce Internet traffic. In addition, it is very important to store the right content at the right time in caches to make effective use of caching. An informative decision has to be made as to which videos are to be evicted from the cache in case of cache saturation. Therefore, the best cache replacement algorithm is the algorithm which dynamically selects a suitable subset of videos for caching, and maximizes the cache hit ratio by attempting to cache the videos which are most likely to be referenced in the future. In this paper we study the most popular cache replacement algorithms (OPT, CC, QC, LRU-2, LRU, LFU and FIFO) which are currently used in video caching. We use simulations to evaluate and compare these algorithms using video popularities that follow a Zipf distribution. We consider different cache sizes and video request rates. Our results show that the CC algorithm achieves the largest hit ratio and performs well even under small cache sizes. On the other hand, the FIFO algorithm has the smallest hit ratio among all algorithms.

KEYWORDS

Cache update, Hit Ratio, Video Popularity, Zipf Distribution

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COMPUTER VISION-BASED FALL DETECTION METHODS USING THE KINECT CAMERA: A SURVEY

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ABSTRACT

Disabled people can overcome their disabilities in carrying out daily tasks in many facilities [1]. However, they frequently report that they experience difficulty being independently mobile. And even if they can, they are likely to have some serious accidents such as falls. Furthermore, falls constitute the second leading cause of accidental or injury deaths after injuries of road traffic which call for efficient and practical/comfortable means to monitor physically disabled people in order to detect falls and react urgently. Computer vision (CV) is one of the computer sciences fields, and it is actively contributing in building smart applications by providing for image\video content “understanding.” One of the main tasks of CV is detection and recognition. Detection and recognition applications are various and used for different purposes. One of these purposes is to help of the physically disabled people who use a cane as a mobility aid by detecting the fall. This paper surveys the most popular approaches that have been used in fall detection, the challenges related to developing fall detectors, the techniques that have been used with the Kinect in fall detection, best points of interest (joints) to be tracked and the well-known Kinect-Based Fall Datasets. Finally, recommendations and future works will be summarized.

KEYWORDS

Fall Detection, Kinect camera, Physically disabled people, Mobility aid systems

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TEXT MINING CUSTOMER REVIEWS FOR ASPECTBASED RESTAURANT RATING

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ABSTRACT

This study applies text mining to analyze customer reviews and automatically assign a collective restaurant star rating based on five predetermined aspects: ambiance, cost, food, hygiene, and service. The application provides a web and mobile crowd sourcing platform where users share dining experiences and get insights about the strengths and weaknesses of a restaurant through user contributed feedback. Text reviews are tokenized into sentences. Noun-adjective pairs are extracted from each sentence using Stanford Core NLP library and are associated to aspects based on the bag of associated words fed into the system. The sentiment weight of the adjectives is determined through AFINN library. An overall restaurant star rating is computed based on the individual aspect rating. Further, a word cloud is generated to provide visual display of the most frequently occurring terms in the reviews. The more feedbacks are added the more reflective the sentiment score to the restaurants' performance.

KEYWORDS

Text Mining, Sentiment Analysis, Natural Language Processing, Aspect-based scoring

For More Details : <http://airconline.com/ijcsit/V10N6/10618ijcsit05.pdf>

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